

Effect of variation of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{SiO}_2$ molar ratio on microstructure and thermo-mechanical properties of electrical porcelain insulator

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Abstract : The effect of variation of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{SiO}_2$ molar ratio through substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite from 0–10% (w/w) on microstructural and thermo-mechanical characteristics of standard porcelain composition has been investigated during firing from 1150–1225 °C/2 h. The fired porcelain bodies were characterized by variation in linear shrinkage, bulk density, apparent porosity, flexural strength, X-ray diffraction analysis and SEM study. The remarkable improvement in thermo-mechanical and electrical properties with well interlocked microstructure were evidenced in electrical porcelain composition based on 7.5% substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite during firing at 1200 °C/2 h.

Keywords : Electrical porcelain, substitution, thermo-mechanical properties, microstructure.

Introduction

Triaxial porcelains are vitrified, fine grained ceramic whiteware which primarily composed of clay, quartz and feldspar. Kaolinitic clay is used to impart the plasticity on the porcelain body for safe moulding, shaping and green strength, feldspar provides fluxing action by decreasing firing temperature and silica maintains the shape and structure of the formed article during firing. Porcelains are used for dinner ware, sanitary ware, decorative ware, electrical insulators and in medicine and dentistry¹. For technical purposes, porcelain are categorized into soft and hard porcelain. Soft porcelain is usually composed of 25 mass % plastic clay, 25 mass % silica and 50 mass % feldspar whereas 50 mass % plastic clay, 25 mass % silica and 25 mass % feldspar is used for hard porcelain. The clay transforms to metakaolin at temperature ranging from 420–660 °C, depending on amount and nature of the alkali content or other impurities present in the batch material^{2,3}. Metakaolin converts into Al/Si-type spinel just before crystallization of primary mullite at about 1000 °C. The fluxing material usually involves a low melting aluminosilicate such as nepheline syenite and other soda or potash feldspars. Feldspar

reacts with the other components upon firing to form liquid or glass at temperature as practiced (1200–1300 °C) during industrial production. The liquid fills gap and voids in the microstructure, leading to densification of the porcelain.

Ideal electrical porcelain bodies always lack mechanical strength due to the presence of crack caused by volume contraction of the silica particle during polymorphic inversion of β quartz to α quartz on cooling below 573 °C.

The demand for high tension insulator in electrical industries has been increased in the phenomenal way in terms of both quantity and quality to combat the drastic increase in power transmission voltage over long distance electricity transmission with least leakage losses. The distinct improvement in respect of its dielectric properties as also of its physical properties like thermo-mechanical strength and ability to withstand severe environmental condition for years together are absolutely essential. The body composition of high tension insulator has been originally based on the conventional triaxial porcelain with certain major modifications.

Improvements of mechanical properties of electrical porcelain have been studied by partial replacement or eliminating the quartz with kyanite⁴, alumina^{5,6}, sillimanite sand⁷, fly ash⁸, silica fume⁹, with a mixture of rice husk ash and silica fume¹⁰ respectively.

The present investigation deals with the evolution of improved high tension insulator through partial substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite to the ideal triaxial porcelain composition, specially in relation to its thermo-mechanical and electrical properties. Alumina porcelain bodies are being derived by partial substitution of quartz with calcined bauxite. The paper communicates the effect of such substitution on thermo-mechanical and micro structural characteristics of the alumina porcelain insulator.

Experimental

In composing aluminous porcelain raw materials used were ball clay (Rajasthan, India), feldspar (Mihijam), quartz (Bihar, India), calcined bauxite (Sourastra, India), china clay (Rajmahal, India). All the above materials were taken in the fine powder form and directly used without purification. The chemical analysis of the raw materials was carried out following standard method of silicate and alumino silicate analysis. The results showed that the impurities were within the limit and would not grossly affect the fired properties of porcelain body. The typical chemical analysis of raw materials is presented in Table 1. Different sets of batch composition based on increasing proportion of calcined bauxite by partial replacement of quartz from 0–10% w/w are given in Table 2. The required proportions of ingredients as per respective batch composition were wet milled in a pot mill using alumina grinding media and 30 mass % water for 10 h. The slurry was dried at 110 °C for 2 h and pulverized. The pulverized mass was kept in air tight bottle. The briquettes were prepared from pulverized mass at

pressure of 1000 kg/cm² in a hydraulic press, dried and finally fired from 1150–1225 °C in a muffle furnace with 2 h fixed soaking period in each case. The fired bars were tested for different physical properties to examine the degree of sintering. Particle size distribution of each batch was determined using a laser diffraction particle size analyzer. Linear shrinkage was determined by measuring the dimensional change of the rectangular bars before and after firing. Bulk density and apparent porosity of the fired samples were determined by the conventional water boiling method. The bending strength/MOR was measured by three point bending method. The coefficient of linear thermal expansion of the fired specimens was determined using NETZSCH dilatometer at a heating rate of 5 °C/min. The microstructure of etched surface of sintered porcelain samples was ascertained by SEM study (Quanta, FEI make, Holland). The identification of crystalline phases in fired compacts was performed by XRD analysis in Philips automatic X-ray diffractometer (XPRT PRO PW-3071) using Cu-K α radiation at the scanning speed of 2°/min. The sintered specimen was tested for respective breakdown voltage using a high voltage dielectric tester (Model DTS-100D) having a maximum output voltage of 100 KV as per ASTM-D3755. The specimen thickness was kept below 3 mm in order to avoid the maximum probability of pores and crack in measuring region. Then the

$$\text{Dielectric strength} = \text{Breakdown voltage/Thickness}$$

Results and discussion

The purity of raw materials and formulation chosen for electrical porcelain insulator play a crucial role on the quality and performance behavior of the finished product. All the raw materials are chemically analyzed and results of chemical analysis are given in the Table 1.

Table 1. Chemical analysis of raw materials used in formulation of electrical porcelain (wt%)

Raw materials	Chemical constituents (wt%)								
	LOI	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	CaO	MgO	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O
Quartz	0.11	99.64	0.15	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.02
Feldspar	0.33	66.78	17.74	0.15	0.01	0.16	0.02	12.48	1.93
China clay	12.49	49.98	34.04	1.40	0.83	0.18	0.10	0.21	0.05
Calcined bauxite	–	5.87	84.03	2.70	3.99	2.20	–	–	–
Pyrophyllite	3.00	72.20	20.32	0.27	0.13	0.10	0.10	2.46	0.40

Table 2. Batch composition (% by weight) of electrical porcelain insulator

Batch No.	Raw material in wt%					
	China clay	Ball clay	Pyrophyllite	Feldspar powder	Quartz powder	Calcined bauxite
B1	6	41	6	17	30.0	0
B2	6	41	6	17	25.0	5.0
B3	6	41	6	17	22.5	7.5
B4	6	41	6	17	20.0	10.0

The batch composition (wt%) and corresponding oxide compositions for electrical porcelain bodies containing increasing proportion of Al₂O₃ : SiO₂ molar ratio are shown in the Tables 2 and 3.

Table 3. Oxide equivalent of insulator batches (wt%)

Constituents	Batch No.			
	B1	B2	B3	B4
SiO ₂	69.07	64.38	62.03	59.68
Al ₂ O ₃	20.28	24.48	26.57	28.67
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.72	0.84	0.91	0.98
Al ₂ O ₃ : SiO ₂ molar ratio	0.1731	0.2239	0.2524	0.2831

The linear shrinkage vs firing temperature relationship for electrical porcelain insulator bodies with increasing substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite are graphically represented in Fig. 1.

lain body firing shrinkage increases steadily showing an inflection at 1200 °C for all the batches following which distinct reduction of firing shrinkage value was noticed. Around sintering range, ingredients forming enough glass or re-precipitation of crystalline phases filling the gaps and voids which lead to densification of the body. However, higher firing shrinkage is noted with progressive substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite. This may be related to conversion of residual quartz into mullite crystal. The maximum firing shrinkage of 11.04% has been observed corresponding to 10% (w/w) substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite to the base composition. The initial replacement of 5.00% (w/w) quartz by calcined bauxite in base composition showed a definite reduction of firing shrinkage than that of base composition which may be caused by the volume expansion caused by conversion of quartz

Fig. 1. Variation of linear shrinkage with temperature in different electrical porcelain bodies.

It is evident from Fig. 1 that with increasing firing temperature and alumina content in electrical porce-

to crystaballite or trydimite in presence of calcined bauxite. The sharp rise of firing shrinkage with firing

temperature indicated a high degree of sinterability of the triaxial body at 1200 °C. The partial substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite maintains shrinkage values within reasonable limit, as such, neither crack nor distortion is detected in the sintered body.

The degree of densification is normally manifested via the magnitude of apparent porosity. From Fig. 2, it is evident that the apparent porosity diminishes sharply to 0.3% only at 1225 °C in all batches although base composition still retains a apparent porosity of 2.78% under the same condition. More or less fully densified bodies are derived in quartz substituted bodies at 1225 °C signifying that the substitution of quartz by bauxite shows a positive mineralizing action towards the development of sintered porcelain insulator body.

The bulk density increased steadily with increase in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiO}_2$ mole ratio in the body.

Mechanical strength of sintered alumina porcelain is an important criteria for its structural application. The Fig. 4 indicated that remarkable improvement of modulus of rupture in quartz substituted alumina porcelain over that of base porcelain composition. Batch B3 bodied with 7.5% substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite exhibits significantly high MOR as 1599 kg/cm^2 fired at 1200 °C. Again, the modulus of rupture is increased progressively with increase in firing temperature up to 1200 °C following which a slight reduction in MOR occurs at the temperature of 1225 °C. This fact may be related to the formation of glassy phase beyond the critical limit and dissolution of crys-

Fig. 2. Variation of apparent porosity with temperature in electrical porcelain body.

The Fig. 3 depicts the bulk density vs firing temperature relationship of electrical porcelain body. This reveals that irrespective of quartz substitution by calcined bauxite, the significant improvement of bulk density has been accomplished in porcelain insulator at any given temperature of firing and approached to the maximum value at 1225 °C. It is interesting to note that bulk density as high as 2.54 g/cm^3 was achieved with 10% (w/w) substitution of quartz by bauxite at 1225 °C. Densification (in such system) is obviously achieved by partial rearrangement and vis-

talline phase in the fired body. The correlation between flexural strength and bulk density results of the fired bodies is well established. With increasing alumina content through replacement of quartz by calcined bauxite to the substantial enhancement of flexural strength of the sintered insulator samples during firing at 1200 °C and above may be attributed to (i) absence of residual quartz, (ii) formation of mullite and (iii) the presence of compatible secondary phase like corundum. The increase in strength is partly due to improved morphology of mullite needles. However

Fig. 3. Variation of bulk density with temperature in electrical porcelain body.

Fig. 4. Variation of MOR with temperature in electrical porcelain body.

the greater strength of insulators with increased bauxite substitution may be related to dispersion strengthened glassy matrix from the corundum particles. These particles perhaps act as barrier to crack propagation and limit the size of Griffith's flaw, thereby increasing the MOR.

Powder XRD patterns of electrical porcelain samples

fired at 1200 °C (Fig. 5) clearly shows the sharp peaks of mullite and quartz as principal major crystalline phases. However, with progressive substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite from B1 to B4, relative peak intensities of mullite phase gradually diminishes with stronger existence of corundum phase. The quartz phase is found to exist in all the samples of electrical

Fig. 5. Powder XRD patterns of electrical porcelain bodies at 1200 °C for batch B1, B2, B3 and B4 respectively.

porcelain although declined continuously from B1 to B4 compacts.

SEM micrographs of etched surface of B1, B3 and B4 electrical porcelains without or with substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite and fired at 1200 °C are presented in the Fig. 6 [(a), (b) and (c)]. The micrographs clearly revealed that the B3 and B4 batches

substituting upto 7.5% (w/w) quartz by calcined bauxite exhibits excellent microstructure with uniform distribution and better interlocking of acicular mullite and elongated corundum grains. On the other hand, the base porcelain composition consists of much elongated mullites from the excessive grain growth which are randomly distributed in the glassy matrix. This may

Fig. 6. SEM micrographs of etched surface of (a) B1, (b) B3 and (c) B4 electrical porcelain bodies fired at 1200 °C.

be responsible for exhibiting poor mechanical and thermal behavior in the base porcelain body.

The coefficient of thermal expansion of the different porcelain composition measured at different temperature interval of 20–250 °C and 20–650 °C are given in Table 4. Cristoballite undergoes α - β transformation at about 250 °C accompanied by large expansion during heating. The higher thermal expansion values of B1 batch is attributed to that phase transformation. The thermal expansion diminishes steadily with increased substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite to the studied batches.

Table 4. Thermal expansion co-efficient of different porcelain insulator bodies

Temperature interval (°C)	$\alpha K^{-1} \times 10^{-6}$			
	B1	B2	B3	B4
20–250	2.20	2.00	2.00	2.10
20–650	7.01	6.60	6.50	6.40

The primary mullitization reaction occurs during sintering of triaxial body by transformation of meta kaolinite to mullite with simultaneous expulsion of SiO₂. This amorphous silica then reacts with Al³⁺ ions available from bauxite to yield either mullite or precipitate as α -alumina phase. This transformation can result in a dense microstructure which is responsible for improvement of mechanical strength as well as low coefficient of thermal expansion in alumina porcelain bodies.

The thermal shock resistance results of aluminous porcelain insulators due to substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite exhibit distinct improvement of 4 cycle to 7 cycles against B1 to B3 samples followed by sharp reduction to 5 cycles only for B4 samples.

The changes in dielectric strength of sintered aluminous porcelain compacts due to increasing substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite fired at 1200 °C is given in Table 5.

The dielectric strength of sintered aluminous porcelain bodies is prominent which increases with increasing Al₂O₃/SiO₂ mole ratio in the batches. It attains a highest value of 31.42 KV/mm corresponding to Al₂O₃/SiO₂ mole ratio of 0.2524 followed by a reduction upto final Al₂O₃/SiO₂ mole ratio of 0.2831.

Table 5. Dielectric strength of the sintered aluminous porcelain insulators bodies

Batch code	Al ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂ molar ratio	Average dielectric strength (KV/mm)
B1	0.1731	25.16
B2	0.2239	27.61
B3	0.2524	31.42
B4	0.2831	28.76

Conclusion

From the densification study on the development of aluminous porcelain insulator, the following conclusions may be drawn :

- (i) The increasing substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite upto 7.5% only to the base insulator composition significantly improves thermo-mechanical properties as well as even microstructure of the porcelain body during sintering at 1200 °C.
- (ii) The 7.5% substitution of quartz by calcined bauxite to the parent porcelain composition results in more or less fully sintered high alumina porcelain at 1200 °C.
- (iii) The powder XRD analysis of B3 aluminous porcelain sample with Al₂O₃/SiO₂ molar ratio of 0.2524 reflects the substitution of quartz by the well crystalline mullite and corundum as principal crystalline phases and quartz as minor phases.
- (iv) SEM micrograph of B3 alumina porcelain sample with Al₂O₃/SiO₂ molar ratio of 0.2524 exhibits well interlocked and coherent microstructure with uniform distribution of acicular mullite and hexagonal corundum grains within glassy matrix.
- (v) The B3 aluminous porcelain body with Al₂O₃/SiO₂ molar ratio of 0.2524 during sintering at 1200 °C attains a significant dielectric strength as high as 31.42 KV/mm.

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